

Floods

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How can we detect flood events with SAR?

February 16, 2023

In this Story Map we will show how Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images can be used to map floods that occur as part of ecosystem dynamics or disaster events. The capabilities presented here are focused on L-band radars such as NISAR (NASA-ISRO SAR Mission).

Background

In populated areas, flooding can result from heavy rainfall and storm surge associated with hurricanes and typhoons. Flood extent maps provide critical guidance to first responders following extreme weather events. In some ecosystems, flood is an integral part of seasonal dynamics that animals and plants must adapt to. In both cases, researchers

need to accurately map temporal changes in surface water. This includes water under low vegetation, water in urban areas, water under tree canopies, and open water not associated with vegetation (See [NISAR White Paper](#)).

Sizing Up Floods from Space: NASA Science for U.S. Flood Response

How to interpret SAR flood images?

SAR sensors send microwave pulses and record the strength of the signal reflected off the ground and back to the sensor, also referred to as the backscatter. By convention, SAR images are displayed in grayscale with bright areas indicating stronger detected signal or backscatter. The examples below show dry and flooded sites observed on a single date, as well as changes that can be observed when comparing images before and after a flood event. In general, radar brightness is highest over flooded forests and tall vegetation, while short vegetation and open water will appear dark.

L-band SAR image acquired over Pedee River, South Carolina on September 23, 2018

Case Study

Hurricane Florence

Hurricane Florence was a category 4 hurricane (August 31 - September 18, 2018) that caused significant freshwater and storm surge flooding along the coast of North and South Carolina. From September 17 through September 23, UAVSAR

(NASA JPL's L-Band airborne radar and NISAR testbed instrument) flew five times over the Pee Dee River in South Carolina to collect data on flooding from the hurricane.

Swipe below to see SAR acquisitions from during and after Hurricane Florence along the Pee Dee River in South Carolina. In the left image captured on September 17th, there is already significant inundation along the Pee Dee River, but the right image from September 23rd captures further rapid expansion of inundated vegetation (bright) and open water (dark).

Hurricane Florence flooding along the PeeDee River, South Carolina. Image Credit: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/thescang/44830694601/in/photostream/>

Left Image: during Hurricane Florence (September 17, 2018). Right Image: after Hurricane Florence (September 23, 2018).

Below is a subset of the Pee Dee River in an area of rapidly expanding flooding extent. The first image is an optical acquisition from Google Earth. A portion of the Pee Dee River is in the lower left corner. Moving left, this subset is composed

of forested areas and agricultural fields with shorter vegetation. Notice the flood advancing between the September 17th to 23rd SAR images. The ability to detect changes in flooding extent is relevant for rapid response in disaster scenarios, particularly near inhabited areas.

Pee Dee River

Google Earth Optical Imagery

Swipe through to compare a two SAR images over the Pee Dee River in South Carolina to an optical image from Google Earth.

The river is visible in the lower left corner, while the rest of the image largely consists of forested areas and agricultural fields.

Pee Dee River

September 17, 2018

This grayscale SAR backscatter image was acquired near the Pee Dee River in South Carolina.

The bright regions in the left portion of the image are areas of inundated forest. Notice how the flooding has not yet extended to the forests and fields in the right half of the image.

HIGH

LOW

Radar backscatter in the HH polarization

Pee Dee River

September 23, 2017

This SAR grayscale image was acquired several days later. The inundation has rapidly expanded from the river, visible in the image as the new bright areas of inundated vegetation.

Some of the fields with agriculture or shorter vegetation have also flooded. These now appear darker than the previous acquisition, since open water has lower backscatter return than open fields.

HIGH

LOW

Radar backscatter in the HH polarization

In the next image, see if you can find inundation based on brightness. Swipe through to compare SAR (left) and Optical (right) images over the Napo River, a tributary to the Amazon River in Ecuador and Peru. Notice the bright features in the SAR image. These are areas of inundated forest below the canopy not visible in optical acquisitions.

UAVSAR (right) and optical image (left). Left credit: Google Earth / Maxar Technologies.

Technology

Why SAR?

Credit: NASA SAR Handbook.

Synthetic Aperture Radars (SARs) transmit microwave pulses and receive the echoes that backscatter from the Earth's surface. The amount of signal that is backscattered depends upon the properties of the objects on the surface. This backscatter information can be transformed into high-resolution radar remote-sensing

products with detailed information about surface characteristics.

Radar can penetrate cloud cover and operate day or night, which can prove particularly useful during flooding events from storms when there is persistent cloud cover. With all these capabilities, radar can be leveraged for flood mapping and detection in both vegetated and non-vegetated areas.

Radar is highly sensitive to the dielectric properties of water. As an active technology, long radar wavelengths can penetrate the vegetation canopy and detect water on the ground underneath the vegetation. Radar can also detect areas of open water because most of the energy is scattered in the forward direction from the water's smoother surface, so radar returns from open water are 'radar dark'. However, when there is water below vegetation, the pulses can be reflected back towards the receiver by the vegetation, bouncing twice, i.e., from water and vegetation. In fact, backscatter from water below trees can be very bright.

NISAR (NASA-ISRO SAR) is an upcoming radar instrument collecting data in the L-band wavelength (23.8 cm). The longer L-band wavelength can penetrate further into vegetation compared to other common SAR sensors measuring in C-band. NISAR will provide high-resolution, near-global, and continual mapping of Earth's natural resources and hazards, such as flooding.

Explore the NISAR Sample Data Product Suite, or planned NISAR data products and their product specifications, here: <https://nisar.jpl.nasa.gov/data/sample-data/>

Radar Scattering and Polarizations

Radar data is collected at different polarizations, or combinations of horizontal and vertical radar waves (i.e. HH, HV, etc.). For example, the images shown in this Story Map are HH, which denotes a horizontally emitted, horizontally collected wave. Each polarization is a separate data product

generated by the radar, and the different polarizations have unique interactions with the ground cover.

The expected scattering mechanisms in a flooded area are described below:

- **Specular / Surface Scattering:** occurs when there is a smooth surface, such as open water. In specular scattering, the signal scatters away from the radar, and as a result, open water appears dark in the image.
- **Rough Scattering:** can occur where some, but not all, of the signal scatters away from the radar. This could be due to wind roughening on open water or areas of shorter vegetation.
- **Double Bounce Scattering:** occurs when most of the signal is returned to the sensor, and these areas appear very bright in the image. This can occur in areas of flooded vegetation due to the interaction pulse scattering from both the smooth water surface and vegetation that sticks out of the water.
- **Volume Scattering:** is most common in vegetated areas as the signal interacts with all components (leaves, branches, trunk, etc.) of the canopy before returning to the sensor.

Credit: NASA SAR Handbook

Credit: NASA SAR Handbook

Making a Flood Map

For flood applications, the HH channel from NISAR will be the most relevant due to stronger backscatter returns from open water, compared to HV, which is more suitable to detect vegetation. HH has higher sensitivity to surface and double bounce scattering, while HV is more suitable for volume scattering detection.

A model is usually employed to infer inundation classes from a backscatter image. The simplest approach is to identify a range of backscatter values associated with different classes. We expect the lowest backscatter values to be associated with open water, but the threshold will vary depending on the study site being considered. The example below from Martinez and Le Toan (2007) shows a classification for the Amazon forest.

Credit: Martinez and Le Toan (2007)

Credit: Martinez and Le Toan (2007)

The map below made by North Carolina researchers (Salem and Hashemi-Beni 2022), shows how multi-temporal images can be used to classify permanent water (in blue) and flood water (in yellow) in areas impacted by Hurricane Florence.

Credit: Salem and Hashemi-Beni (2022)

References and Further Reading

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